

Performative Classroom Activities and the Discourse Competence Among Grade 10 Students

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Abstract:– Discourse Competence is essential to communicate effectively and efficiently in real life situation. Competence in speaking can equip anyone in the communication process in sending accurate and clear messages and information. However, acquiring and enhancing speaking skills particularly, discourse competence could be an agony among students nowadays. Thus, teachers need to employ some strategies and activities in the classroom to better assist the learners in enhancing their discourse competence. The purpose of this study is to determine the effectiveness of using performative classroom activities in enhancing students' discourse competence. The study used a quasi-experimental research design which students undertaken pre-performance and post-performance through interview and conversation to gauge their oral discourse competence. The respondents of the study were thirty (30) Grade 10 students for both experimental group 1 and 2. The study was conducted during the third grading period of academic year 2022-2023. The result revealed a significant difference between the pre-performance and post-performance scores of the student- respondents from both experimental group 1 and 2 which imply that the use of performative classroom activities helped students enhance their discourse competence. This indicates a significant increase on their performance in terms of interview and conversation. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected.

Keywords:–*Conversation, Discourse Competence, Interview and Performative Classroom Activities.*

I. INTRODUCTION

It is one crucial part in one's life to communicate and share ideas. Communication using the English language is very important to be learnt, mastered and be competent at. Learning English language is increasingly becoming the very goal of many people around the globe in the present-day world. The ability to speak and use well English language is one of the most essential skills a person should acquire. In this globalization era, where competition among people throughout the world is strong, mastering English is a must. It is now becoming a necessity to have effective communication skills, particularly discourse competence.

Bhagat and Huang (2018) asserted that memorized knowledge/information does not last long in learners' minds, because it is not related or connected to their real lives. Learning will be enhanced and retained through

classroom practices and performances for effective learning is not only about memorizing and recalling the concepts but also applying those concepts into practice which are useful in everyday experiences. The knowledge of underlying grammatical principles, knowledge of how to use language in a social context to fulfil communicative functions and knowledge of how to combine utterances and communicative functions with respect to discourse principles are significant to enhance learners' communicative competence) [1].

It was believed that effective learning and enhancing discourse competence can be attained through classroom experiences and performances which concepts can be applied and practiced. Experience-based learning is more effective for imparting knowledge and useful to students in the real world. Students learn best from experience. Through performative classroom activities, students have the chance to explore the learning processes by experimenting and practicing critical thinking skills. This makes it easier for children to transfer what they've learned in different contexts.

Communication of English language is a complex learning and one that any of us have difficulty mastering. Therefore, this requires a tool and approach that can comprehensively deal with the enhancement of discourse competence. The performative classroom activities allow learners to grow emotionally and socially as well as academically, fully equipping them for the complexities of their next step in life. Communication is common in that it is something that we spend most of our time doing, but the ability to make sense of and improve our communication takes competence that is learned through deliberate study, personal reflection and usual practice.

One of the challenges at Calubcob I National High School is the difficulty in communication using English language of most Grade 10 students. This was observed during the first day of the class and it was proven and analyzed as the days go by. This is the agony of both the English teacher and students for learning would not be effective and possible most particularly nowadays that learners have learning gaps due to pandemic. They need learning recovery and continuity and must remain engage and enthusiastic in the learning process.

It was observed that most of the Grade 10 students are not engaged in every lesson and hesitant to interact verbally with the teacher or among each other. In most cases, there

were few students who answered the questions given by the teacher. Despite the motivation given by the teacher, they were passive. Worst, there are times when no students are responding to teachers. This scenario was alarming and frustrating to both parties.

The researcher found many problems concerning communication using the English language particularly speaking English in class as if almost sixty percent (60%) of the students cannot understand her; thus, she found her self-obliged to use translation to make them understand what she is saying. It is frustrating on the researcher's part to use some Filipino language during English class just to make the students understand well the lesson. Only 40% Grade 10 students can confidently speak, write and perform during English class. The researcher needs tips to make her job easier and make her student to be communicative competent, most particularly in oral discourse. She adheres that no one will be left behind in her class in terms of communication.

It was observed that students lack self-confidence in using English language to communicate with others. They failed to express their thoughts because it is not easy for them to find the words when they are asked to share in class. They were reluctant to participate during class discussions and found it difficult to construct ideas in their mind and think for the right words to answer. However, it is natural and easy for them to use their mother tongue in the class. They shift to their mother tongue whenever they are asked to discuss a specific topic. Unfortunately, they are unable to express their ideas. With this, they must be motivated to learn and love speaking English.

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

This study attempted to determine the effects of Performative Classroom Activities on the Discourse Competence of Grade 10 Students in Calubcob I National High School, Calubcob I, San Juan, Batangas.

- Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:
 - ✓ What is the mean pre-assessment score of Experimental Group 1 before using the performative classroom activities such as games and role play in terms of interviews and conversations?
 - ✓ What is the mean pre-assessment score of Experimental Group 2 before using the performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate in terms of interviews and conversations?
 - ✓ What is the mean post-assessment score of the Experimental Group 1 after using the performative classroom activities such as games and role play in terms of interviews and conversations?
 - ✓ What is the mean post-assessment score of the Experimental Group 2 after using the performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate in terms of interviews and conversations?
 - ✓ Is there a significant difference between the mean performances of the Experimental Group 1 before and

after using the performative classroom activities such as games and role play?

- ✓ Is there a significant difference between the mean performances of the Experimental Group 2 before and after using the performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate?
- ✓ Is there a significant difference between the mean performances of the Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 in the pre-assessment before using the performative classroom activities?
- ✓ Is there a significant difference between the mean performances of the Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 in the post assessment after using the performative classroom activities?

II. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quasi-experimental design. The process of conducting research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of intervention or treatment but that do not use randomization. In general, the goal is to determine the effect of a factor or independent variable on a dependent variable. In this research design, there were two intact groups of classes involved.

The first group was the experimental group 1-a group who used role play and games while the second group was the experimental group 2 who used small group discussion and debate.

The students were selected based on their performance in English during the First Quarter. In this study, the researcher used pre-assessment and post-assessment before and after implementing the performative classroom activities to enhance respondents' discourse competence.

The students were also assessed using the pre and post-performance in terms of interview and conversation before and after implementing the performative classroom activities. The respondents were tested using this method to see if the performative classroom activities aided Calubcob I National High School Grade Ten students in enhancing their discourse competence using the English language.

➤ *Respondents of the Study*

The study was conducted to the Grade 10 students of Calubcob I National High School for the school year 2022-2023. Particularly, the thirty (30) Grade 10 Eagle students (experimental group 1) and the thirty (30) Grade 10 Heron students (experimental group 2).

➤ *Sampling Technique*

Clustered sampling technique was used to provide a diverse range of this study relevant to the enhancement of discourse competence of Grade 10 Students. Cluster sampling is a sampling technique which is not individual but a group of individuals who are naturally together (Ary, 2010) [2].

The researcher used only two classes as the samples in this research. The first class was class A (30 students from

10-Eagle) as the experimental group 1 and class B (30 students from 10 Heron) as the experimental group 2. Grade 10 consists of five sections with total population of one hundred seventy-four (174). The two classes used by the writer represented the three existing classes in Grade 10. In addition, the researcher used only class A and B because based on the result of the first quarter test and performances in that school, these two classes gained similar average achievements and performances.

The thirty students from the two groups were selected using their grades in English during the first quarter. They were the students who obtained 80-89 grades in English or the non-honour students. Class A (Grade 10 Eagle) was chosen as the experimental group 1 which was taught using performative classroom activities such as role play and games while class B (Grade 10 Heron) was chosen as the experimental group 2 which was taught using performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate.

Furthermore, the grade 10 class was chosen using a cluster sampling technique with the consideration that the section was heterogeneously grouped.

➤ *Research Instruments*

The main tools used in this study were the researcher-made interview guide questions and situations for conversation supported by rubrics for scoring highlighting the discourse competence. While the implementation of performative classroom activities was highlighted on the teacher-made DLL.

The guided oral interview was designed and conducted to assess the students' oral discourse competence. The chosen respondents from both experimental group 1 and experimental group 2 answered the same set of questions orally applying the same procedures. The researcher served as interviewer and took every chance to know her students better with targeted 5 interview questions.

This study also used conversation to assess respondents' oral discourse competence. The teacher prepared five types of conversation with situations and topics to portray. Each type of conversation and situation tested the discourse competence of each student in both experimental groups. Both experimental group 1 and experimental group 2 were grouped into ten. Each group consisted of three members. They were tasked to present the conversation within one to two minutes. They were graded individually using the researcher-made rubric. Their performances were recorded. The same instrument was used during the pre and post-assessment.

The rubric used for interview performance observed six criteria namely: communication, body language, posture and eye contact, general attitude, responses to questions and over-all demonstration of interview skills. These criteria used effectively assessed the oral discourse competence of the students. The possible scores were 4 (excellent), 3 (good), 2 (fair) and 1 (poor).

The researcher also crafted a rubric for conversation performance which used six criteria namely: volume, fluency, posture and eye contact, pronunciation/clarity, content/grammar and over-all demonstration of conversation skills. These criteria employed effectively assessed the oral discourse competence of the students. The possible scores were 4 (excellent), 3 (good), 2 (fair) and 1 (poor).

Furthermore, the researcher prepared the DLL used in executing the performative classroom activities in enhancing the discourse competence. The teacher-researcher used the same procedures in terms of the execution of the daily lesson except to the performative classroom activities employed. The teacher employed games and role plays for experimental group 1 while small group discussion and debate for experimental group 2. These performative classroom activities were used in different parts of the DLL. They were highlighted in the teacher's DLL.

➤ *Research Procedures*

The researcher gathered the necessary materials needed in the study. The researcher designed the interview guide questions and situations of conversation as instruments that focus on discourse competence. To ensure the quality of the instruments, her adviser and other panel members reviewed them. The researcher-made instrument was validated by at least three English experts.

Following the validation of the instruments by the experts, the researcher prepared the request letters for her study. First, the researcher obtained permission from the panel members, her adviser, and the dean to conduct the study. She then requested permission to conduct the study, as well as a data sharing agreement, in a letter to the division office.

Upon the approval of request, the researcher asked permission from the Principal of CNHS with a letter of endorsement to administer the study among Grade 10 students.

After the grant of request permission from the respective offices, the researcher then proceeded to the conduct of the study. The researcher oriented the students and ask permission to their parents through a letter. The researcher conducted pre-assessment through a performance in terms of interview and conversation. The recorded videos were assessed by three chosen evaluators using the crafted rubrics. Grade 10 students were chosen using the clustered sampling technique that used in this study with the consideration that the section is heterogeneously grouped.

Experimental Group 1 students were treated with performative classroom activities using role play and games in daily lesson while small group discussion and debate for Experimental Group 2. The researcher prepared DLL highlighting the performative activities employed in each experimental group. The teacher executed and followed the parts of the DLL. The performative classroom activities were used as motivation, springboard, presentation of the

lesson, discussion or even in application part. These were employed daily for four consecutive weeks.

The first step in the performative classroom activities was to develop skills among students in conducting small group discussion, debate, games and role play as employed in different parts of the lesson to ensure effective learning and discourse competence. The objective is to use English language while learning the lessons and concepts in English subject. Most particularly, the performative classroom activities were used as the springboard of the lesson, presentation of the lesson, part of discussion, abstraction and application.

Performative classroom activities were predicated on the idea that applying the skills and employing learning into experience and practice inside the classroom is a vital component of language learning and enhancing discourse competence. The researcher identified where the students were having difficulty and struggling in terms of communication using the English language. The researcher discovered where the students were having difficulty in terms of discourse competence. This established the basis for what she will need to teach and focus on throughout the lesson.

Two performative classroom activities were performed every day. After the implementation of performative

classroom activities in the experimental class 1 and 2, the researcher administered/conducted the post-assessment in terms of interview and conversation which is of the same level of questioning as to pre-assessment to both groups.

In terms of interview, each student was given one minute to answer one question. The rubric to be used was well-explained. Students were properly oriented regarding the activity. Meanwhile, in terms of interview

The discourse competence of the students was assessed using an actual/oral performance which were graded using a rubric through video recordings.

The researcher stated the purpose of the study, the importance of the respondents' participation, and the assurance that the responses would be kept confidential.

➤ *Statistical Treatment of Data*

The researcher used mean, SD and percentages for descriptive analyses of pre-assessment and post-assessment results. On the other hand, t-test was used to test if there is a significant difference between the mean pre-assessment and post-assessment result of the respondents from both experimental groups in terms of interviews and conversations after being exposed to Performative Classroom Activities such as games, role plays, small group discussion and debate.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Mean Pre-Assessment Scores of Experimental Group 1

Discourse Competence	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Interview	11.28	1.15	Satisfactory
Conversation	10.58	1.23	Satisfactory
Over-all	10.93	1.04	Satisfactory

Legend: 19.20-24.00 Excellent, 14.40- 19.19 Very Satisfactory, 9.60-14.39 Satisfactory, 4.80-9.59 Fair, 0.00-4.79 Unsatisfactory

Note. Table 3 summarizes the discourse competence of the respondents from Experimental Group 1 in terms of interview and conversation during pre-assessment before using performative classroom activities such as games and role play.

Experimental Group 1 obtained 11.28 mean with standard deviation of 1.15 for the interview while 10.58 mean with standard deviation of 1.23 for the conversation. Experimental Group 1 got an over-all mean of 10.93 and 1.04 over-all standard deviation.

Based on the recorded mean pre-assessment scores, students from Experimental Group 1 had a satisfactory performance in terms of interview. Some of the students speak clearly during the interview with lapses in sentence structure and grammar. Most of the students had fidgeted movements, and observed minimal use of physical gestures, facial expressions, and body movements. Almost all students do not look at the interviewer, have minimal eye contact and do not have good posture. Students were somewhat interested in the interview through showing little

enthusiasm. It was observed that students gave not well-constructed responses, sounds rehearsed and unsure. They showed potential during interviews, yet, demonstrated limited proficiency and interview skills in a general confident manner.

Even though they attained satisfactory performance in terms of interview, they still need to enhance their discourse competence. The individual performance exemplified did not match their grade level. Since, the result reflected the mean performance, individually, they need further improvement to be more competent.

Meanwhile, they showed a satisfactory performance during their performance in conversation. They exerted their effort; however, their volume was not always loud enough and sometimes not be heard. They spoke haltingly with long pauses. They observed average posture and had minimal eye contact. The pronunciation was not all clear and students were difficult to understand. The conversation consists of a few details related to the scenario and situation provided. Students mostly use correct vocabulary with some errors in

grammar and sentence structure. All in all, they demonstrated limited proficiency and competent conversation skills during the pre-performance.

With this result, they still need some improvement for them to be competent individuals in terms of discourse. Effective conversation skills were shown by each respondent from the experimental group. They need time to enhance their competence through constant practice and exposure to classroom activities.

This can be achieved using role play and games in the teaching-learning process. It was mentioned in Palermo

(2019) that In the Philippines, oral communication skill has become an essential tool for someone to be successful in his academic endeavour since engagement to classes often, uses English language as its medium of instruction) [3]. Oral communication skill appears to be the most important skill since the students who know the language are usually referred to as speakers of that language. Thus, their discourse competence must be enhanced. This can be supported by the findings of a study conducted by Krebt (2017) that there is a significant improvement in the speaking skill of the experimental group of students using role play and game) [4].

Table 2 Mean Pre-Assessment Scores of Experimental Group 2

Discourse Competence	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Interview	10.32	1.35	Satisfactory
Conversation	9.08	1.66	Fair
Over-all	9.70	1.27	Fair

Legend: 19.20-24.00 Excellent, 14.40- 19.19 Very Satisfactory, 9.60-14.39 Satisfactory, 4.80-9.59 Fair, 0.00-4.79 Unsatisfactory

Note. The table reflects the mean pre-assessment scores of Experimental Group 2 which test the discourse competence of the respondents in terms of interview and conversation before using performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate.

This denotes that respondents from Experimental Group 2 obtained 10.32 mean and 1.35 standard deviation during the conduct of interview while 9.08 mean and 1.66 standard deviation during the conduct of conversation. An over-all mean of 19.40 and an over-all standard deviation of 1.27 were noted.

It is seen that before using performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate that student from Experimental Group 2 had satisfactory performance during pre-performance in interview while noted a fair performance for conversation. Experimental Group 2 marked an over-all fair performance during pre-assessment.

Despite the recorded satisfactory performance during pre-assessment in terms of interview, it was noted that speaking was unclear with lapses in sentence and grammar. Their volume was appropriate. Constant movement of hands and feet were noted. Minimal use of physical gestures, facial expressions and body movements distracted in the interview process. The posture and eye contact were not effectively

observed. Some of the students had a lack of interest and enthusiasm about the interview. Some students provided limited answers and they failed to elaborate and explain. A demonstration of competent interview skills in a generally confident manner was noted. While a fair performance in terms of volume, fluency, posture and eye contact, pronunciation/clarity, content and grammar and over—all demonstration of conversation skills was noted during their performance of conversation.

With these results, it can be interpreted that they find difficulty in communicating and expressing their ideas particularly during conversation because they lack self-confidence. This can be supported by the study of Inayah & Lisdawati (2017) that students' low self-confidence forms them into students who are not motivated in learning English. Therefore, it is necessary to change attitudes so that someone who has courage and good self-confidence will certainly shape the character of students who are able to speak English. In cases like this the teacher must be able to determine how students can be willing to grow confident in practicing speaking English. Teachers can encourage students by utilizing various strategies which can certainly increase students' self-confidence. Debating can be used brilliantly to boost students' speaking in English. The application of debate in classrooms will drive out students' fear of the English language and improve their fluency, pronunciation, and vocabulary) [5].

Table 3 Mean Post-Assessment Scores of Experimental Group 1

Discourse Competence	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Interview	20.56	1.60	Excellent
Conversation	20.90	1.59	Excellent
Over-all	20.73	1.54	Excellent

Legend: 19.20-24.00 Excellent, 14.40- 19.19 Very Satisfactory, 9.60-14.39 Satisfactory, 4.80-9.59 Fair, 0.00-4.79 Unsatisfactory

Note. The table shows the mean post-assessment scores of Experimental Group 1. Their discourse competence was

evaluated in terms of interview and conversation after employing performative classroom activities such games

and role play.

It can be seen from the data presented that the respondents recorded 20.56 mean and 1.60 standard deviation for the interview and 20.90 mean and 1.59 standard deviation for the conversation. Experimental Group 1 discourse competence obtained an over-all 20.73 mean performance and 1.54 over-all standard deviation.

The respondents attained an excellent performance in terms of interview during post-assessment. After using performative classroom activities such as games and roleplay, students speak clearly and distinctly with few lapses in sentence structure and grammar usage. They even speak concisely with correct pronunciation and the volume is appropriate. Occasional shifting, average use of physical gestures, facial expressions and body movements in a manner which enhanced the interview process were observed. They were able to sit up straight, observe good posture and establish eye contact with interviewers during the interview 80-90% of the time. Most of them showed interest and enthusiasm about the interview process. They gave well-constructed responses as compared to the pre-assessment while some hesitations and confusion were observed. In general, they appropriately utilized interview skills in an enthusiastic, motivating and engaging manner.

Furthermore, an excellent performance in terms of conversation during post-assessment was noted. After employing games and role play, the students were able to appropriately utilize conversation skills in a confident manner. Students usually speak loud enough to be heard. They always speak fluently with few hesitations. Good

posture was observed. They established eye contact with the people involved during the conversation 80-90% of the time. Most words were pronounced clearly so that they were clearly understood by the audience. The conversation focused mainly on the situation and scenario provided. They mostly used correct vocabulary with few errors in grammar and sentence structure. The conversation was clear and followed a logical sequence.

Based on the findings and discussions above, it proved that performative classroom activities can enhance students' oral discourse competence. These leads the students to have a better discourse competence which help them to communicate in real life situation. Performative classroom activities also help struggling students who usually stay quite in the classroom to be more active because it gives an equal chance and stress-free learning environment for each student to speak. These activities can reduce anxiety and agony during English class which make the students highly motivated and more confident to speak in the learning process.

This clearly shows that there is a great improvement in the performance of the students after using performative classroom activities such as games and role play. The result can be strengthened by a concept that roleplay is a complete range of communication technologies to develop language fluency, to promote student interaction during the class, to increase students' motivation, and to share responsibilities between teacher-students. (Rojas, 2018) [6]. It was also proven in research conducted by Dewi, (2017) that using communicative games in improving students' speaking skills) [7].

Table 4 Mean Post-Assessment Scores of Experimental Group 2

Discourse Competence	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Interview	17.80	2.16	Very Satisfactory
Conversation	19.39	1.38	Excellent
Over-all	18.60	3.27	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 19.20-24.00 Excellent, 14.40- 19.19 Very Satisfactory, 9.60-14.39 Satisfactory, 4.80-9.59 Fair, 0.00-4.79 Unsatisfactory

Note. The table presents the mean post-assessment scores of Experimental Group 2. This reflects the discourse competence of the respondents in terms of interview and conversation after using performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate.

As pictured out in the table, the respondents got 17.80 mean and 2.16 standard deviation for interview while 19.39 mean and 1.38 standard deviation for conversation. The post-assessment scores provide an over-all mean of 18.60 and 3.27 over-all standard deviation.

The students in Experimental Group 2 had noted a Very Satisfactory performance for interview and an Excellent performance for conversation during post-assessment. An over-all Satisfactory performance was reflected in the table.

The students showed a good performance in terms of communication. Body language, posture and eye contact were excellently observed during the performance. They showed basic interest in the interview and performed enthusiastically during the interview process. They provided good responses to questions and sometimes showed hesitation, yet their genuine and confident answers were felt. To sum up, they demonstrated a very satisfactory performance and competence during post-assessment in terms of interview.

Meanwhile, an excellent performance after using performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate was recorded during conversation. A commendable performance and observation were observed in terms of volume, fluency, posture, eye contact, pronunciation, clarity, content and grammar. Therefore, they demonstrated proficient and competent conversation skills in a confident manner during the post-performance in terms

of conversation.

With this, it can be concluded that the performative classroom activities employed in the teaching process such as debate and small group discussion significantly contribute

to enhance the performance of the students. These research findings are also in line with the statement that debate is an appropriate technique to improve students' speaking skills (Arung, 2016) [8].

Table 5 Test of Difference between the Mean Performances of the Experimental Group 1 before and after using the Performative Classroom Activities Such as Games and Role Play.

Discourse Competence	Before		After		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Interview	11.28	1.15	20.56	1.60	8.530	29	.000
Conversation	10.58	1.23	20.90	1.59	2.497	29	.001
Over-all	21.86	2.07	41.46	3.08	2.931	29	.000

Legend: If the p-value < 0.05, then it is statistically significant.
If the p-value > 0.05, then it is NOT statistically significant.

Note. Table 5 presents the test of difference between the pre-performance and post-performance scores of the students from Experimental Group 1 who were exposed to performative classroom activities such as games and role play.

It is seen that there is a significant difference between the students' pre-performance and post-performance scores after the students exposed to the use of performative classroom activities such as games and roleplay in terms of interview (p-value=0.000) and conversation (p-value=0.001) all variables are less than 0.05 level of significance.

It implies that after the learners were exposed to the use of performative classroom activities such as games and role play, students' discourse competence was enhanced, specifically in conversation, which had the greatest change in the mean of pre-performance and post-performance. On the other hand, performance in the conducted interview also show great students' improvement.

A significant increase in student's performances using games and role play was noted. Students were engaged in the activities. They became more motivated to learn and active during the execution of the lesson. They were enjoying while learning-less stress and pressure. Thus, they learn effectively and were able to develop their discourse competence without noticing it. The conduct of these performative activities provided a great avenue of acquiring knowledge and skill as well as practicing it. These were reflected on the students' outputs, quizzes and performances.

Also, most of their teachers testified that a great improvement on their performances were shown in other subjects. They became more confident in responding to teachers' questions. They were more eloquent in exchanging ideas among their classmates. They were hooked in all the classroom activities given. These excellent transformations were rooted to the integration of performative classroom activities such as role play and games during English class.

In addition, the students showcased their discourse competence in different school's programs and activities. They were enthusiastic in interacting with others using the English language. Excellent performances in other subjects were also noted. These were evident on their written and oral performances. Teachers were amazed on their transformation and considered them equipped in dealing their future endeavour.

With this, students were able to enhance their discourse competence using games and role play and knew how to apply it in terms of interview and conversation. They were able to use performative classroom activities that made sense in enhancing oral performances. Majority of the students were able to communicate their thoughts confidently in front of the class. They were able to express their ideas clearly and can respond to situations based in real-life context. They were not hesitant to exchange thoughts and became more engaged in the learning process.

The improvement of the students' performance scores indicates that students enhance their discourse competence. It can be concluded that communicative games can help the students to be more confident to speak English because they do not feel that they are in the teaching and learning process and make a mistake without having feeling of failure. This can be proven by the claims of Ibrahim, (2017) that using communicative games in the process of language teaching-learning could help all students to feel comfortable and more confident in acquiring a new language) [9].

It was highlighted in the study of Reyes (2014) that to teach is to engage students in learning; thus, teaching consists of getting students involved in the active construction of knowledge. The aim of teaching is not only to transmit information, but also to transform students from passive recipients of other people's knowledge into active constructors of their own and others' knowledge such as engaged pedagogy and performative teaching. Hence, performative classroom activities shaped Grade 10 students to be competent in oral discourse) [10].

Table 6 Test of Difference between the Mean Performances of the Experimental Group 2 before and after using the Performative Classroom Activities Such as Small Group Discussion and Debate.

Discourse Competence	Before		After		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Interview	10.32	1.35	17.80	2.16	3.385	29	.000
Conversation	9.08	1.66	19.39	1.38	6.016	29	.000
Over-all	19.40	2.53	37.19	3.27	5.872	29	.000

Legend: *If the p-value<0.05, then it is statistically significant.*
If the p-value>0.05, then it is NOT statistically significant.

Note. Table 6 indicates the test of difference between the pre performance and post-performance scores of the students from Experimental Group 2 who were exposed to performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate.

It can be interpreted that there is a significant difference between the students’ pre-performance and post-performance scores after the students exposed to the use of performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate in terms of interview (p-value=0.000) and conversation (p-value=0.000) all variables are less than 0.05 level of significance.

In other words, students’ pre and post performances have a significant increase. It also shows higher scores of the students in the post assessment. This means that integrating performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate was effective in enhancing students’ oral discourse competence.

With this, students were not only able to understand the lesson but were able to develop their discourse competence. Performative classroom activities such as SGD and debate became a tool for them to be well-versed in terms of communication and interacting with their classmates. Majority of the students were able to develop their discourse competence by performing given classroom activities effectively and were able to create and explain themselves using the given activities in expressing ideas. All these were reflected on the result of students’ quizzes and daily performance tasks.

Aside from the mentioned evidence, students excelled not only in English subject but also in other subjects which use English as the medium of instruction. They can apply the skills and competence gained even in school programs and activities. Their teachers noticed their improvement and commended their performances. This entails the great impact of using the performative activities during English class.

Students found these activities effective and motivating. They were able to improve their speaking skills for they need to talk and express while doing the activity. They considered these useful in enhancing their competence. In addition, they found these significant in real life context for they need to communicate, interact and collaborate.

Moreover, discourse competence acquired through using small group discussion and debate in everyday learning experience was shown in terms of interview and conversation. They were able to use performative classroom activities which are significant in enhancing oral performances. Students in Experimental Group 2 clearly express their ideas and thoughts during class discussions and performances. This can be reinforced by the study conducted by Weimer (2009) which pointed out that it is through discussions that students learn communication skills as well as the ability to cooperate. Discussions and sharing of ideas, which happens during group discussions, help the students to gain a better perspective) [11].

Table 7 Test of Difference between the Mean Performances of the Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 in the Pre-Assessment before using the Performative Classroom Activities.

Discourse Competence	Group 1		Group 2		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Interview	11.28	1.15	10.32	1.35	2.875	58	.024
Conversation	10.58	1.23	9.08	1.66	1.533	58	.063

Legend: *If the p-value<0.05, then it is statistically significant.*
If the p-value>0.05, then it is NOT statistically significant.

Note. The test of difference between the pre performance scores of the students from Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 before using the performative classroom activities was shown in Table 7.

The table reveals that there is a significant difference between Experimental Group 1 students’ pre-performance and Experimental Group 2 students’ pre-performance before

the students exposed to the use of performative classroom activities in terms of interview (p-value=0.024) which is less than 0.05 level of significance. However, there is no significant difference between the pre-performance of Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 before the teacher employed performative classroom activities in terms of conversation (p-value=0.063) which is greater than 0.05 level of significance.

Based on the data presented, it can be interpreted that Experimental Group 1 performs better with a mean of 11.28 than Experimental Group 2 with a mean of 10.32 during pre-assessment in terms of interview. Students from experimental group 1 were more enthusiastic than students from experimental group 2. Also, experimental group 1 is more confident. There are great differences in the scores of the students from Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 in terms of interview. On the other hand, though there are differences, Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 obtained close scores during pre-performance. Therefore, there is no significant difference on their performance. They have the same level of discourse competence and performance in terms of conversation before using performative classroom activities.

As reflected in the results, despite the potential exemplified by the students, performative classroom activities were needed to enhance their skills and competence. This alarming skill and competence were reflected on their quizzes, summative test and periodic test. Also, their recorded scores for daily performance tasks were not satisfying and did not match their Grade level. The same agony was shared by their teachers in other subjects. They were not able to express themselves clearly.

In terms of interview, it was hard for them to establish contact with the interviewer. They just provided limited and

short answers. Some of them were not able to construct even simple sentences, they just answered using few words. Unnecessary movements and gestures were also noted. Most particularly, they were not confident while doing the interview.

While in conversation, there were no effective exchange of ideas. Students were not enthusiastic during the performance. They were passive as they interact with their classmates. Then, an eye-to-eye contact was not effectively established. Ideas and lines were not clearly expressed.

With the noted results of pre-assessment, games, role plays, SGD and debate were significant. They helped the students to be more enthusiastic and engaged in the learning process. Thus, the researcher prepared DLL employing performative classroom activities that would help them enhance their discourse competence.

The researcher considered Roslaniec (2018) who suggested that communication is the skill many students find challenging to acquire especially in a second language) [12]. Even if the Philippines is doing fine in terms of English competency, the country still needs to step up its efforts in improving the English language teaching and learning, developing it as a vital skill of the workforce (Cabigon, 2015) [13].

Table 8 Test of Difference between mean Performances of the Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 in the Post Assessment after using the Performative Classroom Activities.

Discourse Competence	Group 1		Group 2		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Interview	20.56	1.60	17.80	2.16	7.440	58	.000
Conversation	20.90	1.59	19.39	1.38	1.619	58	.058

Legend: *If the p-value < 0.05, then it is statistically significant.*
If the p-value > 0.05, then it is NOT statistically significant.

Note. The table displays the difference between the mean performances of the Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 in the post-assessment after being exposed to performative classroom activities.

The result implies that there is a significant difference between Experimental Group 1 students' post-performance and Experimental Group 2 students' post-performance after the students exposed to the use of performative classroom in terms of interview (p-value=0.000) the variable is lower than 0.05 level of significance.

Meanwhile, it can be interpreted that there is no significant difference between Experimental Group 1 students' post-performance and Experimental Group 2 students' post-performance after the students exposed to the use of performative classroom in terms of conversation (p-value=0.058) the variable is greater than 0.05 level of significance.

In other words, students' post- performances in terms of interview have a significant difference. The table reflects that Experimental Group 1 got higher mean than

Experimental Group 2. After employing performative classroom activities in both experimental groups, experimental group recorded a better performance than experimental group 2.

It was observed that experimental group 1 were more participative and motivated to learn. They considered games and role plays as engaging activities. They were stimulated in every activity employed by the teacher thus, resulted to an excellent performance. They regarded these activities as effective strategy in creating an effective and engaging learning atmosphere. The teacher was able to hook the interests of the students and made them understand the lesson easily. These improvements were reflected on their quizzes, summative test and even on their periodic test. Excellent performances during daily performance tasks were also noted. The competence gained through the conduct of the study was also exemplified in other subjects.

On the other hand, SGD and debate greatly helped the students from experimental group 2 to enhance their discourse competence. These activities provided an interactive communication among students. Students were

able to connect, express, exchange thoughts and ideas while listening to one another. These skills were significant in real-life context.

However, there is no significant difference in the post-performance of both Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 because students obtained almost the same scores as reflected in the mean performance in terms of conversation. The same improvement was noted. They were more at ease and comfortable while doing the conversation because they were in a group interacting with one another unlike the interview which was just between the teacher and the student. Students were more comfortable doing the conversation than the interview. There were more interaction and exchange of ideas during conversation. Also, there was a situation given, thus they were carried away with their emotions and can easily relate and express. Both experimental groups excelled in conversation, therefore, obtained almost the same level of competence and performance.

A better performance of Experimental Group 1 was illustrated in the table. This indicates that performative classroom activities such as games and roleplay were more effective than debate and small group discussion. They found games and role play as more engaging and interactive. They were stimulated with these activities and turned them to be more enthusiastic in the learning process. Meanwhile, SGD and debate were also useful for experimental group 2. Only, there were more pressure and ideas needed in doing these mentioned activities.

This can be supported by Altun (2015) stated that role-play techniques influence the development of speaking skills of language learners. Through repeated exposure to language elements in role-play techniques, learners learn the language incidentally. Furthermore, role-play techniques provide a good opportunity for learners to learn the everyday language) [14]. Syarif (2020) Speaking is the most essential skill that needs to be mastered by the students. The students may have some difficulties related to the lack of practice in the classroom which makes their speaking skill level is low. One technique can be used to improve students' speaking skill is Communicative Games) [15].

It also shows higher scores of the students in their post-performances. Both Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 noted a satisfying improvement on their performances. They became more confident in terms of communicating with others using the English language. They were able to clearly express their ideas and a commendable performance during English class was observed after the treatment. They turned to be competent individuals who are always ready to engage themselves in a discussion or conversation.

Therefore, based on the results presented above, Trejo (2008) was correct on his proposed task activities which refer to the types of performative classroom activities which can help develop students' communicative competence such as games, information gap, dialogues, situational practice,

reading, and listening. The task activities will then serve as useful media which can stimulate students to interact and speak up in the classroom) [16]. Similarly, Caicedo (2015) has also agreed that games, role plays, situational practice, information gap, debate, dialogue, and small-group discussion are highly recommended to enhance students' communicative competence) [17].

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

- There is a significant difference between the mean performance of the Experimental Group 1 before and after using the performative classroom activities such as games and role play. The students discourse competence was enhanced. They became enthusiastic in using the English language and embodied competence while expressing ideas. Thus, the hypothesis was rejected.
- There is a significant difference between the mean performance of the Experimental Group 2 before and after using the performative classroom activities such as small group discussion and debate. The students can confidently and competently converse and communicate using the English language during English class and even in real-life context after using the treatment. Thus, the hypothesis was rejected.
- There is a significant difference between the mean performance of the Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 in the pre-assessment before using the performative classroom activities in terms of interview. Their skills and competence were not on the same level before using the performative classroom activities. However, there is no significant difference between the mean performance of the Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 in the pre-assessment before using the performative classroom activities in terms of conversation. The same level of skills and competence were noted before the treatment.
- There is a significant difference between the mean performance of the Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 in the post assessment after using the performative classroom activities in terms of interview. Evidently, experimental group 1 performed better than experimental group 2. On the other hand, there is no significant difference between the mean performance of the Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 2 in the post assessment after using the performative classroom activities in terms of conversation. Both experimental groups have the same level of improvement.

➤ *Based on the Results and Conclusions of the Study, the Following Recommendations are Hereby Suggested:*

- Since the study revealed that the use of performative classroom activities is effective in enhancing the discourse competence of the students, English teachers are encouraged to employ these activities in the instruction. Teachers may also use these activities not just for Grade 10 English but also in the other grade levels. Moreover, teacher of different areas of

discipline may also use these for these were applicable to all and since discourse competence is vital on education.

- The school administrators and department heads may give support on the use of Performative Classroom Activities since the study found out significant improvement in the discourse competence of the students. They may be encouraged to provide trainings or SLAC sessions relevant to the use of Performative Classroom Activities not just for English but also in other areas of discipline.
- Future researchers may use this as reference for their study. They are encouraged to conduct similar study not only in English, but also in other subjects.

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